

A) STRENGTHS OF THE CHESTNUT RESOURCE

Factor	Factor weighting score														Factor			
	More important than							Equal	Less important than									
Good availability of the resource	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Vocational training initiatives
Provision of ecosystem services (cultural and protection)	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Diversity of wood assortments
Strong knowledge of the chestnut resource and its products	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Generational change of forest entrepreneurs
Diversity of wood assortments	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Vocational training initiatives
Strong knowledge of the chestnut resource and its products	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Vocational training initiatives
Vocational training initiatives	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Generational renewal of forest entrepreneurs
Good availability of the resource	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Provision of ecosystem services (cultural and protection)
Diversity of wood assortments	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Strong knowledge of the chestnut resource and its products
Diversity of woody assortments	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Generational renewal of forest entrepreneurs
Provision of ecosystem services (cultural and protection)	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Generational renewal of forest entrepreneurs
Provision of ecosystem services (cultural and protection)	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Strong knowledge of the chestnut resource and its products
Good resource availability	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Diversity of wood assortments
Provision of ecosystem services (cultural and protection)	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Vocational training initiatives
Good resource availability	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Generational renewal of forest entrepreneurs
Good availability of the resource	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Strong knowledge of the chestnut resource and its products

B) WEAKNESSES OF THE CHESTNUT RESOURCE

Factor	Factor weighting score																Factor	
	More important than								Equal	Less important than								
Weakly harmonised forest management	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of public support for the provision of ecosystem services (PES)
Negative spotting value	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Technological defects in wood
Negative stumpage value	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Land pathology and orographic context
Land pathology and orographic context	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Weakly harmonised forest management
Negative landscape value	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of public support for the provision of ecosystem services (PES)
Technological obsolescence and poor innovation support in processing companies	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Technological timber defects
Weakly harmonised forest management	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Wood technological defects
Land pathology and orographic context	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Wood technological defects
Land pathology and orographic context	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of public support for the provision of ecosystem services (PES)
Technological timber defects	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of public support for the provision of ecosystem services (PES)
Weakly harmonised forest management	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Technological obsolescence and poor support for innovation in processing companies
Negative spotting value	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Weakly harmonised forest management
Land pathology and orographic context	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Technological obsolescence and poor support for innovation in processors
Technological obsolescence and poor support for innovation in processing companies	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of public support for the provision of ecosystem services (PES)
Negative spotting value	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Technological obsolescence and poor support for innovation in processors

C) OPPORTUNITIES OF THE CHESTNUT RESOURCE

Factor	Factor weighting score																	Factor
	More important than								Equal	Less important than								
Enterprise networks	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Forest certification and quality labels
Chestnut research projects	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Forest certification and quality labels
Forest certification and quality labels	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Increased civil society awareness of ecosystem services
Enterprise networks	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Increased civil society awareness of ecosystem services
Chestnut Research Projects	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Increased civil society awareness of ecosystem services
Chestnut research projects	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Enterprise networks

D) THREATS OF THE CHESTNUT RESOURCE

Factor	Factor weighting score																		Factor
	More important than								Equal	Less important than									
Climate change	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Depopulation of mountain areas	
Climate change	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Uncertainty about subsidies and incentives for the forest-wood sector	
Depopulation of mountain areas	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Uncertainty about subsidies and incentives for the forest-wood sector	
Lack of market knowledge and strong foreign competition	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Uncertainty about subsidies and incentives for the forest-wood sector	
Climate change	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Lack of market knowledge and strong foreign competition	
Depopulation of mountain areas	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Little knowledge of the market and strong foreign competition	